

DISCOURSE ANALYSIS IN THE SELECTED PLAYS OF POST SECOND MILLENNIUM YORUBÁ PLAYWRIGHTS

OSOBA, BOLANLE KIKELOMO

Department of Nigerian Languages Education,
College of Language and Communication Arts Education,
Lagos State University of Education,
Òtò/Ìjànìkin, Lagos.

E-mail: bolosoba005@yahoo.com

And

ADEKOYA, ELIZABETH OLANIKE

Department of Nigerian Languages Education,
College of Language and Communication Arts Education,
Lagos State University of Education,
Òtò/Ìjànìkin, Lagos.

E-mail: adekoyaeo@lasued.edu.ng

And

ŞÓLÀJÀ, TÈMÍTÓPÉ OLÚKÁYÒDÉ

Department of Nigerian Languages Education,
College of Language and Communication Arts Education,
Lagos State University of Education,
Òtò/Ìjànìkin, Lagos.

E-mail: solajato@lasued.edu.ng

Abstract

Yorùbá drama and its criticism have constituted significant areas of scholarship yet to be explored to its fullest. In addition, previous studies on Yoruba drama have focused on first and second generations of Yoruba playwrights who constitute the first millennium writers. The second millennium Yorùbá playwrights are those who wrote their plays from the year 2000 to date. This paper is thus designed to explore Discourse in three Yoruba Millennium plays. It highlights the various discourse features in the selected plays and the contributions of the writers to the corpus of Yoruba literature. By its very nature, Yorùbá drama is a communal art, incorporating several elements such as mime, dance, costume and narrative art, while Discourse is an integral part of human existence. Findings show that the new millennium Yoruba playwrights have contributed immensely to Yoruba discourse

by using language to highlight the salient features of Yorùbá discourse in the texts. Discourse features such as turn taking-taking, adjacency pairs and elicitation in talk occur severally in the plays, reflecting the Yorùbá discourse situation in the new millennium.

Keywords: The second millennium Yorùbá playwrights, Discourse, conversation, first and second generation.

Introduction

Yoruba drama and its criticism have constituted a significant area of scholarship yet to be explored to its fullest. Previous studies have focused on Yoruba plays generally, but much has not been done on the post second millennium Yoruba plays. The second millennium Yoruba playwrights are those that wrote their plays from year 2000 to date. Many research in form of critical analysis, appraisals, studies of trend issue related to life, characterization, thematization, have been carried out on some Yoruba plays, but much has not been on the discourse analysis of the post second Yoruba playwright. Among works that can be cited on Yoruba drama are Clark (1979), Ögundeji (1981), Arohunmolase (1982), Adeoye (1984), Adegbola (1985) and Ogundeji (1988) to mention a few. This paper highlights the various discourse features in the selected plays of second millennium Yoruba playwrights. The selected plays are Bolanlé Dosunmu's *Igi Elèèrà*, Adéníyì Akangbe's *Èèpà-ń-para rẹ̀*, and Debo Awe's *Àpótí Alákàrà*. This paper concentrates on the written discourse of the play selected.

Discourse

Discourse is an integral part of conversation and human existence. When two people are talking or discussing, a conversation will definitely occur. Discourse is a continuous stretch of especially (spoken) language, larger than a sentence, often constituting a coherent text such as sermon, argument, debate or narrative. It also connotes the use of oral and written language to specific audience, for specific purpose, and in specific setting. Three major characteristics of discourse are appropriateness, purposefulness and coherence. A discourse must be appropriate in the sense that it must suit the situation in question. It must also have a definite purpose and must be coherent. Discourse can also refer to the speech patterns and usage of language, dialects and acceptable statements within a community.

Jawourski and Coupland (1997) assert that any study that examines the language in the social context and investigates social life through linguistic contexts is referred to as socio-linguistics. Social events determine language use just as language mirrors a social event. The kind of language to be used in a party differs from the kind of language to be used where a woman loses his beloved husband. Discourse

goes further to probe how people use their language in their respective social contexts. Language is used to exhibit properties which reflects its organization, coherence, and thematic focus etc. The playwrights under study make use of characters that use various discourses to bring about the general understanding that people give out information when they speak, the information is out with salient features in text.

This paper examines the discourse features under the following sub-headings:

Discourse participant, Turn/Turn taking, Topic Negotiation, Discourse opening/closing, Discourse interruption, Role sharing, Adjacency pairs and Elicitation in talk

Themes in the Selected Plays

The playwrights under study weave their stories on contemporary issues in the society. The issues discussed in their plays are love of money, love affairs, drug pushing, and illicit affairs between men/women.

Theme of Love of Money

In *Apóti Alákàrà*, the love of money is portrayed in the play when *Àńwòó* and *Oyè* are looking for money by all means. After their secondary school education, *Àńwòó's* father advises her to go into teaching profession. She refuses that she can't go into teaching but prefers business. *Bádéjò*, their classmates, comes to encourage them to join Agriculture team proposed by the government. They both refuse. They plan to push drug abroad. *Oyè* and *Àńwòó* are caught at the border and *Oyè* was killed while *Àńwòó* is wounded. She comes back to the village and becomes a casual worker to her classmate that take to Agriculture. *Wọ́núádé* also kills her husband because of money.

In *Igi Elèrà*, *Fúnmiláyo* becomes Chief's girlfriend because of love of money. When *Fúnmiláyo* is in the school, Chief struggles to pay her school fees. gives her money for upkeep etc. After her graduation, she refuses to marry Chief.

Fúnmiláyò: Kín ni Olóyè ẹ̀ ẹ̀ ní kan kò ẹ̀ rí

A rí ẹ̀ ní tó kólé fún obinrin

tí kò si fi ọ̀rọ̀ fífẹ̀ wọ̀ ọ̀...

Nítòotọ̀ ní wọ̀n nàwó fún mi, ẹ̀gbọ̀n

ẹ̀mi náà ná ara fún wọ̀n.

(Igi Elèrà p44)

What has Chief done that no one else has not done

There are men who had built houses for women and didn't marry them

Truly, he spent money on me, but I spent my body too

(Igi Elèèrà p44)

Chief Oreòfèró goes to a herbalist to destroy her life.

Oreòfèró: Bàbá èmi náà mọ. Ọmọ tó bá dájú ẹni
Ó yẹ kí èniyàn náà dájú rẹ
Father; I know. When a child proves stubborn,
One needs to teach her lessons

Fáṣọlá: Agbėti lọmọdé n gbégi elèèrà
Pé Fúnmiláyò ọmọ Atinúkẹ ti digi elèèrà lónií
kí tọmọdé tàgbà máa gbé e ní àgbéju sílẹ.
...No child can carry a plank with ants
Fúnmiláyò has become a plank with ants
Let her be abandoned by the young and old

Fúnmiláyò was cursed that no one will marry her in life; this happens because of love of money

Theme of parent/children relationship

It is common in the society today that parents always show their children love in order to help them to be good citizens. In *Àpótí Alákàrà*, Karimu, Anwoo's father always corrects Àńwòó for all her wrong doings but Anwoo's mother is always backing her up. Karimu corrects Àńwòó concerning the mini-skirt she always wears and flirting here and there, but her mother tells him that he should allow Àńwòó to enjoy her life. At the end of the play, Àńwòó regretted all her evil deeds by serving her classmates as a casual worker. It is pertinent to note that in Yorúbá society, parents are always concerned when their son's wife is not pregnant after marriage. They can go to any length to see that they did all to assist. Bádéjọ complains bitterly about his wife's (Jádesólá) barrenness to his dad, Jèmísi. Ifá oracle is consulted and Jádesólá becomes fruitful.

Theme of love affairs

In the present day society, love issue is very paramount and germane among the youths of these days. In other to woo the girls of these days, they can tell lies, exonerate themselves to be what they are not, put on false identity in the name of

false love. In *Àpótí Alákàrà*, the love issue also ensues between Oyè and Àńwòó. Àńwòó was in love with Oyè, they agreed that they will both travel overseas so that they will cement their love and also have plenty of money. The love issue deprived Àńwòó the sense of listening to her father.

In *Àkàngbé Adeniyi's Èpà-ń-para-rè*, the love issue ensues between Dòtun and Déólá. Bose is the legal wife of Dòtun. Dòtun shifts his love to Déólá, a student in his school. He spends heavily for Déólá by buying clothes, food-stuffs, bush meat e.tc. Towards the end of the play, Déólá uses charm (juuju) to curse Déólá, and Déólá became mad. At this juncture, we must note that there is genuine love in the Yoruba society. Yoruba people show love to their wives by seeing them as mothers, wives, companion e.t.c. The kind of love in the society today as being portrayed by the playwrights are 'fake-love'. The new generation of our youth today does not portray love in its true sense; and this is the reason that there is bitterness and strife at the end of their love affairs.

Theory for the analysis

Sociology of literature has pre-occupied itself with the social commitment of art, the position of the writer in the society and his relationship to that society. It also pre-occupies itself with the social significance of art. Literature is instructive and closely connected to the moral life of man. Literature and sociology are inseparable phenomena. Literature is about what is operational in the society while sociology of literature is about the society. Bamidele (2000) says that literature in its aesthetic form creates a fictional universe where there is a possible verification of reality at the experiential level of man living in the society. It is quite explicit that sociology of literature has common conspectus, which is the understanding of society and the behavior of man in the society.

At this juncture, we shall discuss the documentary approach as it relates to the study of the plays. Hippolyte Taine (1828) uncovered a mine of priceless source material in understanding a society.

Bamidele (2000) asserts that Taine makes three things become paramount in understanding a literary text. These he referred to as race, moment, and milieu. He argues that literary works furnish documents because they are monuments. He stresses that different historical periods succeed in producing a harmonic relationship between genius and the age. The implication of Taine's theory on the relationship of literature is that only the artist is capable of fully expressing his time, and by representing the mode of being a whole nation and a whole age. A writer rallies round him the sympathies of an entire age and an entire nation.

The post second millennium Yoruba playwrights are those who wrote their plays from 2000 to date. They understand fully what is currently operational in the

society; therefore, the treatment of their themes on love and sex, love of money and parent-children relationship etc is in consonance with contemporary happenings in the society. As a Yoruba adage says, *ajá iwòyí ló mọ ehoro iwòyí lé* which means the dogs of this age have the potential of dealing with the hares of this age. The post second millennium Yoruba playwrights know that in this contemporary society, only one that is wealthy is recognized as somebody important in the society in any function or important occasion. The chairperson is always a wealthy man or woman who will be able to donate thousands of Naira not minding how conscientiously or diligently he or she got the money. The present generation cares less about the source of anybody's wealth. What they are after is seeing that they relate with someone who has money. In all the plays under study, the issue of love of money is paramount. The love of money as the Bible says is the root of all evils. Another quotation from the Bible says that money answereth all things; however, one needs to be cautious in looking for money. In Yoruba setting, people also believe that one should aspire to be wealthy, because when someone does not have money, fear will be his/her master. People are so desperate in the society today that they can 'do' and 'undo' just because of money.

Discourse Features Demonstrated by the Playwrights

The playwrights under study are conversant with Yorùbá language, and understand fully what conversation between participants must be. Conversation must be entertaining, humorous, knowledgeable, witty and conspicuous. This is demonstrated by the playwrights under study. Conversation can also create an ambience (atmosphere), a context in which the conversationalists are able to pursue their overt or hidden goals. This is often the function of the kind of conversation called "small talk or chit-chat" (Nerlich and Clarke 2000). When conversing, there must not be conversational accidents or conversational traffic jam. We shall discuss the discourse features under the following sub-headings as mentioned earlier on.

Discourse Participants

It may comprise two or more people taking part in conversation. In the plays under study the discourse participants in *Apótí Alákàrà* by *Débò Awẹ* are *Áńwòó*, *Àdió*, *Oyè*, *Bánjò* and 18 others. In *Igi Elèèrà* by *Bólánlé Oládiméjì Dòsùmú* the discourse participants are *Jèmísi*, *Adétóún*, *Ìfẹpàdé*.

Badéjò Jádesólá and 29 others. In *Èpà-n-para re* by *Adéníyì Àkàngbé*, the discoursants are *Bose Dòtun*, *Adéqlá*, *Dàpò*, *Níyì* and 13 others. It is pertinent to note that the Yorùbá playwrights under study made use of many participants, this may be the reason that made the contents of their plays to be meaningful.

Discourse Opening/Closing

Osisanwo (2003) stresses that discourse opening is that preliminary exchange, no matter how brief. It is the beginning statement in conversation. Discourse closing is when a conversation has ended. The conversation can be terminated when a closing exchange involving paired utterances such as a question and answer. Discourse opening/closing is an integral part of conversation. There must be an opening and closing. The playwrights under study made use of this. In *Igi Eléèrà*, the opening of the discourse starts by Adédòtun, Jemiisi's wife. She is discussing with the witch head, Akérékorò for supporting her during the wedding ceremony of her son.

The play ends with the accident that happens that claims the lives of Babafémi, Ifépadé, Fúnmiláyò and Remilékún. In *Èèpa-ń-para rẹ*, the discourse opening starts with Rántí, both of them are discussing Dòtun, Bose's boyfriend. The play ends tragically, when Dotun's house is burgled by Akilápá and his friends. Dòtun is left with nothing at the end. The playwrights under study demonstrated a kind of discourse style that shows vividly that there is reward for any wrong behaviour. No matter how long it takes, there is always a reward at the end of every action we take. Fúnmiláyò is rewarded with death because of the evil she did to Chief Ọrẹ̀òfẹ̀rọ̀. Likewise, Dòtun also receives sack letter and ends his life tragically.

Turn/Turn Taking

Turn taking is central to discourse analysis. If speaker A is talking, speaker B must be attentive to listen to what A is saying, after that, speaker B will now take his/her turn to speak. The process of each speaker talking when the floor is free is referred to as Turn-Taking. Turn taking is the basic unit of the conversation, is the turn, that is a shift in the direction of the speaking flow. It is a characteristic of normal conversation. Conversationalists do not speak all at the same time, they wait their turn for better understanding of the subject matter. It is very crucial to discourse. In every conversation, there is need for adequate understanding and flow to be observed by the discourse participants. Even though, there is no guiding rule as when to start talking or stop talking, but it seem they have internalized such a system of etiquette that tells participant A when to start talking and when to stop. The playwrights under study demonstrated a high sense of this feature. Participants take turn when it is their turn.

In *Èèpa-ń-para rẹ*, when Déọ́lá and Dòtun are discussing about their love issue, it is done in sequential order.

Dòtun: Déọ́lá, mo fẹ́ ki a jọ máa rin, ki a si
máa fí ọ̀rọ̀ àşiri han ara wa. Bi o kò
bá mò, láti igbà tí mo ti dé ilé -èkọ̀ yin,
ni mo ti ń şàkiyèsi pé bóyá mo lè rí ẹni tí ó lè şéé bá

kówòó

Déqlá: I want to be your man
Let's know each other's secrets
Ever since I joined this school,
I have been thinking about dating you

Déqlá: Ó dára n ó máa wá sí ilé yín
lálalé ki ẹ tó sùn
It's okay, I will be coming to your house
every night, before you sleep

Dòtun: ... Ohun tí mo n sọ ni pé
mo nífẹẹ rẹ, o sì wù mí jọjọ
I mean I love àti pé I'm dying for you
(Èpà-n-para rẹ p 33)

What I am saying that
I love you, and I cherish you
I mean I love you, and I'm dying for you

In the conversation of love above, Dòtun will stop, and Déqlá will take her turn. In Àpótí Alákàrà when Karímu is discussing with Àńwòó about her coming home late at night. Each takes their turn spontaneously.

Àńwòó: Hùn -ùn (ó ta kókó ojú)
Hun-un

Karimu: Wọn tí ẹnu rẹ ní kókórọ ni?
Is your mouth padlocked?

Àńwòó: Hùn-ùn
Hun-un

Karimu: (Ó pa keere mọ Àńwòó) Sàngó ni ó
sọgi gbá o lẹnu tó o fi n sù mi ni
pọn-ọn-ùn, iwọ kàtà ọmọ lásán yìi.

(Apótí Alákàrà p4)

(He moved closer to her) May Sango, the god
Of thunder strike your saucy mouth
you worthless child.

The playwrights under study make use of the turn taking in a unique way.

Discourse Interruption

This occurs when speaker A is talking, and speaker B interrupts or intrudes. It is also called a speech clash. Interpretation is very common during argument, debate, quarrel or even narration of an exciting event by many participants.

This is called speech clash. It can also occur when two people are talking and a third person wants to interrupt his father are discussing, Àbẹ́ọ́, Àńwòó's mother interrupts the discussion.

Àbẹ́ọ́: (pẹ́lú igbónára, ó ta pẹ̀rẹ̀ pẹ̀rẹ̀ súnmo Àńwòó àti
Karimu, ó si fẹ̀rẹ̀é fí igè àyà rẹ̀ li Karimu lulẹ̀) Ẹ má pòkòò
mo omọ mi lẹnu o. Ẹ má bá mi lé e láya lo
Èyàn kàwé mẹwàá, ẹni ó má wà lóminira.
Àlóminira ti wá jẹ?

(Apótí Alákàrà p5)

(with hot temper; she moved towards Àńwòó

and Karimu, and she almost hit fell Karimu with her chest)

Don't shun me. Don't drive away my wife.

Someone studied hard, and you say they shouldn't

be independent

Why won't he be independent?

The discourse interruption also occur when Jẹ̀míisì and Iyádunni are discussing the ill health of Jẹ̀míisì. Adétóún interrupts the discussion because she does not want the children to take good care of their father's health.

Jẹ̀míisì: Iró, n ò lọ, kò ye kí n fí tẹ̀mi
kò bá tiyín. Ó di ilé iwòsàn
mẹta ti mo ti lọ, síbẹ̀ kò sí iyàtò...
it's a lie, I am not to disturb you
I have been to three

hospitals now. Still, no change...

Ìyádunni: A kò lè máa wò yín níran. Ojú wa
ò lè gbà á ki ẹ máa jẹ irora báyii..
We cannot neglect you. We cannot
Be looking at you writhing in pain.

Adétóún: (Ó jágbe mọ Ìyádunni) Dáké n bẹ.
Ẹ gbọ ohun ti bàbá yín sọ.

(Àpóti Alákàrà p 11-12)

(She snapped at lyadunni) Keep your mouth shut.

Listen to your father's comment

The interruption comes in when Adétóún shouts and encourages them to listen to their father's instruction. The playwrights demonstrated this device in a unique way.

Topic Negotiation

This can occur when a speaker feels abandoned or is eager to contribute to the topic at hand. It is an attention-catching device usually embarked upon by a participant, who wants to pave way for the introduction of his own topic of discourse. Topic negotiation occurs when there is a change in the topic hearer. In Igi Elèèrà, Adétóún and Olórí (the dead of the witches) are discussing the event of Adetoun's son's wedding. The topic of discussion changes when the head of the witches is informing Adetóún that the food served is to initiate the members of the choir into their "Tọkọlawà Group".

Adétóún: Mo dúpẹ gidigidi lówó yín fún àdúrótì
yin ní àkókò tí ọmọ mi ẹ igbéyàwó.

I am very grateful for your support

during my child's wedding

Olórí: Haa! A kì í dúpẹ ara ẹni. Ìwọ gan-an
ni a bá dúpẹ lówó rẹ fún iṣẹ
takuntakun ti ó ẹ.

Haa! It is nothing. You are the
one we need to appreciate for
your great efforts

Akérekòrò: Ni ojò ìgbéyàwó ọmọ re, àwọn
ẹgbé akọrin àti àwọn ọmọ ijọ kò mọ pé
oúnjẹ tí a fún wọn jẹ pé láti fi wọ inu ẹgbé ni.

On your child's wedding day, the choir
and members of the church didn't know
that the food we served them was to
initiate them to our group

Adétóún: ... Nitòótọ ni diẹ ninú wọn bínú lọ,
sùgbọn àwọn alátẹnujẹ dúró tití tí a
fi gbé oúnjẹ dé. Wọn gbé e lura tán, ni
wọn bá ara wọn ninú ẹgbé tọkọ
làwa ó ẹ.

(Igi Eléèrà)

... Truly, some of them left in anger;
but the gluttons waited till we brought
food. They ate and found themselves
in our midst.

This feature also comes up when Níyí and Tẹjú are discussing about their love issue. The topic of discussion changes when Níyí tells Tẹjú that she wants her to come as full housewife to his house, but Níyí stresses that **women** always talk of sexual relationship issues more than men.

Niyi láà o káreraya mi
Haa, kudos to you my wife
Tni aya re
Enisyoun wife?
òì kun wákàti náà dé tán.
Owm a lirry, the time is almost here
wàh niuu iwà bee
mo lama..
onenstalk

Téjú: Èwo ni a ní wi, èwò ni o ní sọ?
À ní sọrò sọkòtò, o ní sọrò bẹlítì
Èwo ni ó tún rò dé "orí iṣu jije"?
Your response is not corresponding
with the topic on ground
We are talking of trousers, you are talking
about belt
Which one is "yam eating"?

The topic change from being her full housewife to sexual related issue: "Isu jije". The playwrights under study employ this feature to show the uniqueness of Yorùbá discourse.

Role-Sharing

It is obvious that participants or speakers age, sex, educational attainment, occupation achievement, or social status often determines or affects their roles in a speech event. It must be noted also that there is always a three level distribution for the participants. We have the upper role, middle role and lower role. A king will be regarded as one belonging to the upper role; while someone selling pepper in the market will be regarded as one belonging to the lower role. It shows that the status of the speaker will determine the role s/he will play in the discourse. For example, a student will talk like a student, while a teacher will talk like a teacher. In Èèpà-ń-para rẹ, Dọtun is a teacher, a flirt and drunk. The kind of discourse from him portrays his status.

When Bose is discussing with Dọtun for coming late from school, the following conversation ensues.

Dọtun: Mo ti kúrò ní oḡbà ilé-èkó tipétipé
àmọ mo gba ilé itajà Ààrẹ Àgò lọ ni.
È ṣeun, àmọ ara náà ló ta yín púpọ.
Ṣèbi agogo méréni ni ó ṣeṣe ku iṣéjú
mẹwàá yii?

Èèpa-n-para rẹ (p 14)

I had left the school premises
but I walked past Aare Ago market.

Thank you, but you are just being careful

The time is just ten minutes to four

Dõtun also plays his role well as a drunk. He is at the bar always. Dotun is praising beer, when he is with his friend, Dèbò.

Dõtun: O káre, ajílè ni ọtí jẹ fún agbári
ìsoyè ni ó sì jẹ fún àtári
Bí o bá jin tan, gbogbo ohun ti agbára
rẹ kò ká lójú ayé ni o ó máa ẹ
láìbikità...

(Èèpà-ń-para rẹ p 69)

Well done, beer is manure for the brain

Tẹjú: Èwo ni a ń wi, èwo ni ò n sọ?

It's a memory strengthener

Things you cannot do
on a normal life
You do them with ease

Dõtun and his friend, Dàpò continues to sing for beer as follows.

Lílé: Háàpù ọwọ mi ---- ọmọ ni n ó fifún
Nóbù ọwọ mi ---- ọmọ ni n ó fifún
Sítáotù ọwọ mi ---- ọmọ ni n ó fifún
Ọdẹkù ọwọ mi ---- ọmọ ni n ó fifún (p 70)

Dõtun and Dèbò are praising stout, Noble, Harp as if they (the beers) are human beings. Dõtun is a chronic womanizer and a flirt. He demonstrates this while talking to Déólá to woo her love.

Dõtun: Ọrùn rẹ ẹ rẹgi, ó si ẹ déédé ara
Eléjìkà èyẹ, abèjìkà ẹ gégé ara.
Bí o bá tún wo èso tí Ọlórùn fi
şiké àyà rẹ, rẹgi ló ẹ. Kò kéré kojá
àlà, bẹẹ ni kò tóbi tayọ.
Láifì ọkan pe méjì, ẹwà rẹ kojá

ayé, ó si kojá òrun, bí òsùmàrè tí i
kanlè, tí si i kan ọ̀rùn.
Her neck is well placed
Her shoulders are impeccable to the body.
And if you look at the fruits that God endowed
her on her chest, they are well fitted.
They are neither too small nor too big
Without mincing words, your beauty
is beyond this world and heaven.
it's like the rainbow, that reaches both
earth and heaven.

(Èpà-n-para rẹ 32)

Dòtun: Ohun tí mo ń sọ ni pé, mo ni ifẹ rẹ
O sì wù mí jojọ. I mean I love you
àti pé, I'm dying for you.
I mean I love you
and you are my heart desire,
I mean I love you. Besides, I am
dying for you

If not that he is a flirt, how can someone die for another. All that he is saying is to use sugar coated mouth to woo Déọ́lá. "Gbogbo àlùwàlá ológbò rẹ láti kẹran jẹ ni (all that he is doing is just to see "her skirt")

Bose is Dotun's wife. A woman can over react if she knows that her husband is having marital affairs with another woman outside. The kind of discourse she says to Dòtun portrays that she is a woman. Yorùbá people say, "òrìsà jẹ ń pé méji obìnrin kò dénú". (when a woman says to god that her husband should have two wives, it is never sincere)

When Dòtun and Déọ́lá discuss on money issue, Bose asks about his salary.

Bòsẹ: Owó oşù rẹ náà ni. Iwọ kúkú ti,
wá jìyà láyé ní tìrẹ. Déọ́lá sì wá,
gbádùn ni. Ìgbà tí iwọ bá sáré,

jànnàjànnà kalẹ̀ kiri, òun á sì tẹ̀wó,
gbowó pẹ̀lú irọ̀rùn. Èèdàré,
It is his salary. You have come to life,
to suffer. And Déọ̀lá came to enjoy hers.
When you run helter skelter, she will,
be the one to collect money,

Dòtun: Kò, ní d́áa fún ọ̀ níbi to sọ ọ̀ déun,
It shall not be well with you,

Bòsẹ̀: Tèmi ha ti jẹ́, egbé ẹ̀ni kó làá gúnýán ewùrà fún.
Ìgbà tèmi kò sí nínú ọ̀wọ̀ aláílérò bí tiyín,
This is not my fault,
one does not make pounded yam,
out of water-yam for one's mate,
I do not belong to a senses group like you,

Dòtun: Bàbá àti iyá ẹ̀ laláílérò
(Èèpà-ń-para rẹ̀ p 83)
Your parents are the senseless fellow

Bose becomes furious and the more reason she abuses Dòtun with Èèdàré' (sluggish man), 'aláílérò' (senseless person)

Elicitation in talk

A talk on a topic will usually start from someone, and there will be reaction from an action. There is speaker, usually through questioning is called elicitation in talk, a response or answer from a question. All the playwrights under study make use of this feature. Some are answers to various questions in the plays. Bòsẹ̀ lends Dòtun some money to help her sister to register for West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE).

Bòsẹ̀: Ojọ wo lẹ́ ọ́ fún mi lówó mi o?
Which day will you give me my money?

Dòtun: Owó wo ni mo jẹ́ yín?

Which money?

Bòsẹ̀: Egberún-kan-àbọ náirá owó idánwò
One thousand five hundred naira for exam

Dòtun: Iyè mi fò ó o
I forgot

Bose is demanding her money and Dòtun is responding that he has forgotten about it.

In Igi Elèèrà, when Adétóún is discussing with the Olóri (the head of the witches) to help her deal with her husband.

Akérékorò: Irú àjùlọ wo lo fẹ? Kí a gbé àgbàná lé e
lọwọ ni abi ki a sọ ọ di akúretẹ?
Which superiority do you want?
should we make him spend fruitlessly
or we make him wretched?

Adétóún: N ò fẹ kí ó kú n ò sì fẹ ki ó
rùn, sùgbón mo fẹ ki ó wà bí
aláisi láye...

(Igi Elèèrà)

I don't want him dead or sick
but I want him to live a turbulent life

Adétóún replies that she doesn't want the husband to die, but not to enjoy his life, let him be there as a figure-head man.

In Àpótí Alákàrà, Karimu complains that Àbẹ̀ọ, his wife does not wake up on time. There is a question and answer:

Karimu: Irú wàhálà wo ló wa ẹ tó bẹ̀ẹ?
O gbégi lódò ni àbí o gún ogi?
which trouble have you experienced to that extent?
You carried a log of wood or climbed a tree?

Àbẹ̀ọ: Ó dáa, ẹ má bínu
All right, don't be angry

Àbèò responds and pleads with her husband not to be angry with her.

Adjacency pairs

This is very crucial in discourse. It is a situation where exchange structures in pairs. According to Schegloff and Sacks (1973), adjacency pairs consist of two fundamentally related turns, each made by question/answer, greeting /greeting, challenge. The playwrights under study made use of this feature. In all the plays, there are greetings among the participants always. Adjacency pairs can come in form of invitation/acceptance, request/acceptance, greetings/greetings and question/answer.

In *Apótí Alákàrà*, Karimu, (the husband) greets his wife. There is an exchange of pleasantries between them.

Àbèò: (Ó kúnlè kí ọkọ rẹ) Ẹ káàárò.
(she knelt down to greet her husband) Good morning

Karimu: O káre sẹ dáadáa lo jí?
(Àpótí Alákàrà p 2)
Well done. Hope you slept well?

There is also adjacency pairs between Bose and Ránti, in form of question and answer.

Ránti: Sẹ kò ní wá sí ibí lóníí ní?
Will the person not come today?

Bòsẹ: O tún sẹsẹ n bú iyá tíṣà, bóyá ó ti dé tán báyii
(Èpà-ń-para rẹ p1)
You don't need to worry about that
who knows whether she is almost here already

The question is whether Dòtun will be coming to Bose's place, and the response proves that he might be on the way as of time they are discussing. When Déólá and Dòtun are discussing their love issue, Déólá asks whether Mama Sẹyí will not be angry if she realizes that Dòtun and Déólá are having affairs. She asks.

Déólá: But báwo ni a ti máa sẹ ti Mama Sẹyí sí,
mo mean iyàwó yín?
But what about Seyi's mother
I mean your wife?

Dòtun: Má worry rará. Ọ̀gèdè ni tire yẹn, kò
tó ohun ti à á yọ àdà sí...

(È̀pà-ń-para ẹ p35)

Don't worry about her: Hers is like banana tree
we need not cutlass to bring it down

Dòtun responds that Mama Seyi will not be a blocking stone to their affairs. In Igi Elèrà, when Bádéjọ is reporting to his dad. Jèmiṣi, about how Adétóún is molesting his wife because of barrenness.

Bádéjọ: Bàbá, ẹ e gbọ ohun tí iya mi ń sọ?

Şé ó yẹ ki iyà mi máa ti ojú oníka-mésàn-án kà á?

Father, can you hear what my mother said?

How can my mother be mannerless?

Adétóún: Àimòkan ló ń ẹ ọ

Akọ pépéyẹ ni iyàwó tí o gbé sílé.

(Igi Elèrà 7)

The use of adjacency pairs is common in the Yorùbá settings, greeting is paramount in the society and also, people always ask various questions to clear some issues bothering their mind. The playwrights under study have demonstrated the discourse features in their plays in unique ways. Their style is unique in the sense that there are new trends added to their plays like code-mixing and the use of abuse. The conversational techniques is adequate, the conversation brings humor to readers, the conversationalists were able to pursue their goals, in a way that meaning were decoded from the conversation. Messages were delivered appropriately. Turn taking is predominant in the play, and that gives it out as a structured discourse. Certain words were paired together such as greeting/greeting, and questions/answers. The tempo of their play rises when the play is at the peak giving a kind of suspense to the readers. Although, the play centres on themes on love affairs, children/parents relationship, greed, covetousness, etc along the line, there are several topic changes. The three major characteristics of discourse, which are appropriate, purposeful and coherent were demonstrated by the playwrights under study.

Conclusion

The new millennium Yoruba playwrights have contributed immensely to Yoruba discourse by using language to bring out salient discourse features in the text. It has

been established that turn-taking, adjacency pairs and elicitation in talk etc as discourse features occur severally in the plays. They play an important role by ensuring a better understanding of the predominant themes of love affairs, parents and children relationships and love of money. The reader will have a full grasp of the behavior of nowadays youth.

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